

Morphological and Molecular Characterization of the Nematode *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. (Dorylaimida, Belonidiridae) from Peninsular Spain

Miriam García-Ruiz^{1,*}

¹Departamento de Biología Animal, Vegetal y Ecología, Universidad de Jaén. Paraje “Las Lagunillas” s/n, Edificio B3, 23071- Jaén, Spain.

*Correspondence: E-mail: migarcir@ujaen.es (García-Ruiz)

E-mail: nruiz@ujaen.es (Ruiz-Cuenca); abolafia@ujaen.es (Abolafia); rpena@ujaen.es (Peña-Santiago)

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^sRetired Professor.

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Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis sp. nov. is described, including morphological data, LM and SEM illustrations, and molecular (18S-, 28S-rDNA) analyses. The new taxon is widely distributed in the southern part of the Iberian Peninsula, where it is mainly associated with natural habitats. It is characterized by its 1.57–2.43 mm long body, lip region cap-like and offset by marked constriction, cheilostom slightly flask-like with thick and visibly refractive walls bearing distinct circumoral platelets, odontostyle 9.0–9.5 μm long or almost equal to lip region diameter, odontophore linear, relatively short neck ($b = 6.1\text{--}9.7$), anterior pharyngeal region weakly muscular and bearing a spindle-shaped and valve containing region behind the odontophore base, pharyngeal expansion 113–157 μm long or 44–54% of total neck length, longitudinal vulva ($V = 5057$), tail conoid to subcylindroid (31–47 μm , $c = 37\text{--}59$, $c' = 1.4\text{--}1.9$ in females), spicules 38–40 μm , and five ventromedian supplements with hiatus. The results confirm an intricate scenario for elucidating both the phylogeny and the taxonomy of Dorylaimellinae in particular, and of Belonidiridae in general. The morphological heterogeneity of the group is even more complex than usually assumed, and its internal evolutionary relationships are not well established as the phylogenies derived from the molecular analyses significantly differ depending on the gene considered.

Key words: Description, LSU, Morphology, Phylogeny, SSU, Taxonomy

BACKGROUND

Dorylaims, the representatives of the order Dorylaimida, are very diverse and abundant nematodes. They present a global distribution and dwell in all kinds of soil and freshwater ecosystems, playing important roles in their corresponding trophic webs, often being regarded as good bioindicators of environmental quality (Peña-Santiago 2021a). The most recent compendium of their diversity revealed that the inventory of the group reached 3405 named (3052 valid) species (Peña-Santiago

2021b).

The family Belonidiridae Thorne, 1939, with 305 named (276 valid) species, is one of the most important dorylaimid taxa. Morphologically, it is characterized by the presence of a spiral muscular sheath enveloping its pharyngeal expansion (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1992; Andrassy 2009). Unfortunately, the feeding habits of its members remain very poorly studied, but they are traditionally considered to be omnivorous or predators (Yeates 1967; Small 1987; Peña-Santiago 2021a). Belonidirid taxa appear very widely distributed, with

presence on all continents except Antarctica, but it is in tropical areas where they reach the highest values of species richness (Andrássy 2009).

The genus *Dorylaimellus* Cobb, 1913 *sensu lato* (Peña-Santiago 2021b) includes 94 named (81 valid) species, by far the most diverse and widely distributed belondirid taxon. It displays an extraordinary variation in key diagnostic features (lip region, odontostyle, odontophore, female genital system, tail shape, etc.), which results in an intricate and controversial taxonomy that splits the genus into more than one dozen subgenera, some of them considered valid genera (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980; Siddiqi 1983; Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1992; Andrássy 2009).

The belondirid fauna of the Iberian Peninsula, in particular that of southern areas, is reasonably well known. At present, it consists of seven genera and 15 species, eight of them belonging to the genus *Dorylaimellus* (Jiménez-Guirado et al. 2007; García-Ruiz et al. 2025). Interestingly, one of the most abundant and widely distributed Iberian belondirid taxa was found and morphologically characterized by Peralta (1993) in his PhD thesis, but its description was never published. It was a *Dorylaimellus*-like form that displayed some significant differences with the known members of this genus, which has been repeatedly collected in subsequent nematological surveys conducted throughout the last three decades in Andalusian soils. Very recently, a new population was found in the framework of the European project *Soil O-live* (EU Horizon Program grant No 101091255), and fresh specimens were obtained for molecular analyses. Thus, the present contribution aims to characterize this undescribed belondirid taxon, including morphological and molecular analyses, and to discuss its evolutionary relationships within the family Belondiridae.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling, extraction and processing of nematodes

Soil samples were collected mainly from natural areas in more than 20 localities of Eastern Andalusia, provinces of Almería, Granada, Jaén and Málaga. Nematodes were extracted by centrifugation (Chitambar 2007), based on Jenkins (1964) and/or with Baermann's funnels following the protocol by Flegg (1967) somewhat modified, killed by heat, fixed in 4% formaldehyde, preserved in anhydrous glycerin according to Siddiqi's (1964a) method, and mounted on permanent glass slides that were sealed with paraffin.

Morphological and morphometrical study

Nematodes were measured and photographed using an Eclipse 80i microscope (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with differential interference contrast optics, a drawing tube (camera lucida) and a DS digital camera. Morphometrics include Demanian indices (de Man 1880) and other measurements and ratios, some of them presented in a separate table, and others forming part of the literal description of the species.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

A few specimens preserved in glycerine were selected for their observation with SEM following the protocol proposed by Abolafia (2015). The nematodes were hydrated in distilled water, dehydrated in a graded ethanol-acetone series, critical point dried, coated with gold, and observed with a Zeiss Merlin microscope (5 kV) (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany).

DNA extraction, PCR and sequencing

For molecular analyses, and in order to avoid mistakes in case of mixed populations in the sample, single specimens were temporarily mounted in a drop of 1M NaCl containing glass beads to ensure specimens conformed with the target population. DNA was then extracted from individual specimens as described by Archidona-Yuste et al. (2016). The D2-D3 domains were amplified using the D2A (5'-ACAAGTACCGTGAGGGAAAGTTG-3') and D3B (5'-TCGGAAGGAACCAGCTACTA-3') primers (Nunn 1992; De Ley et al. 1999). The portion of 18S rRNA was amplified using primers 988F (5'-CTCAAAGATTAAGCCATGC-3'), 1912R (5'-TTTACGGTCAGAACTAGGG-3'), 1813F (5'-CTGCGTGAGAGGTGAAAT-3') and 2646R (5'-GCTACCTTGTTACGACTTTT-3') (Holterman et al. 2006). All polymerase chain reaction (PCR) assays were done according to the conditions described by Archidona-Yuste et al. (op. cit.). The amplified PCR products were purified using ExoSAP-IT (Affimetrix, USB products) and used for direct sequencing on a DNA multicapillary sequencer (Model 3130XL genetic analyzer; Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA), using the BigDye Terminator Sequencing Kit V.3.1 (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA), at the StabVida sequencing facilities (Caparica, Portugal) according to the Sanger et al. (1977) method. The newly obtained sequences were submitted to the GenBank database under the accession numbers indicated on the phylogenetic trees.

Phylogenetic analyses

For phylogenetic relationships, analysis was based on 18S and 28S rDNA fragments. The obtained sequences were manually edited using Chromas 2.6.6 (Technelysium) and aligned with other rDNA sequences available in GenBank using the ClustalW alignment tool implemented in MEGA7 (Kumar et al. 2016). Poorly aligned regions at extremes were removed from the alignments using MEGA7. The best-fit model of nucleotide substitution used for the phylogenetic analysis was statistically selected using jModelTest 2.1.10 (Darriba et al. 2012). The phylogenetic tree was generated with the Bayesian inference method using MrBayes 3.2.6 (Ronquist et al. 2012). *Romanomermis culicivora* Ross and Smith, 1976 (DQ418791 and EF417153, for the 18S and 28S rDNA trees, respectively) was chosen as an outgroup. The analysis under the General Time Reversible plus Invariant sites plus Gamma distribution (GTR + I + G) model was initiated with a random starting tree and run with the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) (Larget and Simon 1999) for 1×10^6 generations. A total of 25% of samples was discarded as burn-in. The tree was visualized and saved with FigTree 1.4.4 (Rambaut 2018).

RESULTS

Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis sp. nov.

(Figs. 1–5)

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Measurements: See Table 1.

Description

Type population

Material examined: 12 females and one male from Calar Alto, Almería, Spain.

Adult: Very slender ($a = 50$ – 62) nematodes of medium size, 1.77–2.43 mm long. Body cylindrical, tapering towards both extremities but more appreciably towards the anterior end. Habitus after fixation always strongly curved ventrad, C- to G-shaped. Cuticle two-layered, with fine transverse striation, 1 μm thick at anterior region, 1.5 μm in mid-body and 2.5–3.0 μm on tail; both layers especially distinct at caudal region, the inner one thicker than the outer. Lateral chord 9–12 μm wide or up to two-fifths of body diameter at mid-body, with marked margins and very granular aspect; glandular bodies very abundant throughout the body; lateral pores (when observed under SEM) appearing as narrow longitudinal slits two ‘annuli’ long each (Fig. 5D, F, G). Ventral glandular bodies also abundant and

distinct throughout the entire body. Lip region cap-like, offset by a marked constriction, 2.7–3.0 times as wide as high and less than one-third (29–31%) of body diameter at neck base. SEM observations: oral aperture located in the centre of a small, hexagonal plate surrounded by the inner region of lips; lips separated by radial (longitudinal) incisures, the lateral lips being smaller than the other ones, and separated from these by deeper incisures; inner region of lips forming liplets around the oral plate, offset from the other part of lips by the existence of short transverse incisures; labial (both inner and outer) and cephalic papillae button-like, with a pore at their centre. Amphidial fovea cup-like, opening at level of the cephalic constriction, its aperture 7–7.5 μm or up to four-fifths of the corresponding body width. Cheilostome a truncate cone, somewhat flask-like, 3–4 times as long as wide, with thickened and slightly refractive walls at its anterior half, ending in distinct perioral, also refractive platelets. Odontostyle dorylaimid, slightly fusiform, hardly shorter than lip region diameter, 5–7 times as long as wide, with large aperture occupying one-third to one-half (34–47%) of its length. Odontophore linear (rod-like), 1.5–1.8 times the odontostyle, not always easy to appreciate. Guiding ring simple, located at 6.5–8 μm from the anterior end. Pharynx consisting of a slender and weakly muscular anterior region gradually enlarging into the basal expansion, bearing a thickened, spindle-shaped area 23–25 μm long that contains valves inside, these located at 54–56 μm or *ca* six times the lip region diameter from the anterior end, a differentiation only perceptible in well-fixed specimens; posterior expanded region cylindrical, 10–12 times as long as wide, occupying *ca* one-half (44–54%) of the total neck length, surrounded by a thick dextrorse muscular spiral sheath; gland nuclei obscure. Nerve ring located at 88–93 μm from the anterior end or one-third to two-fifths of the total neck length. Cardia rounded conoid, 12–15 \times 9–10 μm , enveloped by intestinal tissue. Tail convex conoid to subcylindroid, slightly curved ventrad, dorsally convex, ventrally straight or slightly concave, always with an appreciable thickening of cuticle at tail tip; caudal pores two pairs at the posterior third of tail: one lateral, another laterodorsal.

Female: Reproductive system diovarian, with both branches variably long but equally developed, the anterior 116–190 μm long or 7.1–9.6% of body length, the posterior 160–237 μm or 6.9–10.5%. Ovaries relatively small, often not reaching the sphincter level, 56–125 μm , first with oocytes arranged in two or more rows and then in a single row. Oviduct subterminally joining the ovary and consisting of a slender part made of prismatic cells and a well-developed *pars dilatata* with wide lumen inside. A distinct sphincter separates

Table 1. Morphometrics of *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. Measurements in μm except L in mm, and in the form: average \pm S.D. (range)

Population	Calar Alto (type)		Alhama		Moraleta		Órgiva		Sabiote		Santisteban		Total range
	Province	Habitat	Almeria	Pine forest	Granada	Oak forest	Granada	Brushwood	Jaén	Olive	Jaén	Olive	
n	Holotype	Paratypes	Paratype		Paratype		Paratype		Paratype		Paratype		
	♀	11 ♀♀	♂	11 ♀♀	9 ♀♀	9 ♀♀	5 ♀♀	♂	3 ♀♀	6 ♀♀	6 ♀♀	46 ♀♀	
L	2.28	2.12 \pm 0.22 (1.77–2.43)	2.08	1.90 \pm 0.18 (1.57–2.20)	2.02 \pm 0.11 (1.74–2.15)	1.88	1.88 \pm 0.15 (1.69–2.12)	1.88	1.93–2.11	2.06 \pm 0.1 (1.80–2.24)		1.57–2.43	
a	57	54.0 \pm 3.4 (51–60)	57	53.0 \pm 3.0 (49–59)	56.0 \pm 2.3 (51–60)	57	52.5 \pm 4.2 (48–59)	57	53–57	59.8 \pm 3.5 (56–66)		48–60	
b	8.8	8.2 \pm 1.0 (7.0–9.7)	7.7	7.7 \pm 0.7 (6.6–9.2)	7.0 \pm 0.5 (7.0–8.2)	7.2	7.5 \pm 0.3 (7.1–7.9)	7.2	6.1–7.2	7.4 \pm 0.6 (6.6–8.5)		6.1–9.7	
c	51	50.2 \pm 3.1 (46–56)	42	46.9 \pm 3.7 (42–54)	53.8 \pm 3.5 (48–59)	43	46.6 \pm 4.3 (42–52)	43	44–46	48.8 \pm 3.7 (44–53)		42–59	
V	54	53.7 \pm 1.1 (52–56)	-	52.6 \pm 1.4 (50–55)	54.1 \pm 0.9 (53–57)	-	52.5 \pm 1.4 (50–54)	-	53–55	52.3 \pm 1.5 (50–54)		50–57	
c'	1.8	1.6 \pm 0.1 (1.5–1.8)	1.8	1.7 \pm 0.1 (1.5–1.9)	1.5 \pm 0.1 (1.4–1.7)	1.6	1.7 \pm 0.1 (1.6–1.8)	1.6	1.7–1.9	1.7 \pm 0.1 (1.6–1.9)		1.4–1.9	
Lip region diameter	10	9.5–10	9.5	9.0–9.5	9.0–9.5	9.5	9.0–9.5	9.5	9.0	9.0		9–10	
Odontostyle length	9	9	9	9.0–9.5	9.0–9.5	9	9.0–9.5	9	9.0–9.5	9.0–9.5		9–9.5	
Odontophore length	16.5	16.1 \pm 0.2 (16–16.5)	16	15.9 \pm 2.2 (15–16)	15.8 \pm 0.3 (15.5–16)	16	16.1 \pm 0.4 (15.5–16.5)	16	?	16		15–16.5	
Neck length	260	259 \pm 9 (247–278)	271	247 \pm 11 (234–265)	262 \pm 16 (247–295)	262	259 \pm 8 (250–268)	262	289–311	275 \pm 12 (263–294)		234–311	
Pharyngeal expansion length	132	129 \pm 9 (113–147)	130	128 \pm 7 (116–138)	130 \pm 14 (116–157)	130	130 \pm 6 (122–137)	130	147	129.3 \pm 4.7 (126–136)		113–157	
Body diameter at neck base	32	31.5 \pm 2.2 (29–35)	31	30.7 \pm 1.6 (28–34)	30.0 \pm 1.4 (28–32)	28	30.0 \pm 1.3 (28–32)	28	31	30.5 \pm 1.0 (30–32)		28–35	
mid-body	40	39.3 \pm 4.1 (35–46)	36	35.8 \pm 2.0 (32–40)	36.0 \pm 1.5 (34–38)	33	35.8 \pm 0.8 (35–37)	33	35–37	34.3 \pm 1.2 (32–35)		32–46	
anus/cloaca	25	25.8 \pm 1.6 (24–28)	28	24.6 \pm 1.2 (23–26)	24.5 \pm 0.7 (23–26)	28	23.6 \pm 0.5 (23–24)	28	23–25	23.6 \pm 0.8 (23–25)		23–28	
Vulva- anterior end distance	1223	1139 \pm 112 (960–1322)	-	998 \pm 80 (847–1147)	1092 \pm 68 (927–1153)	-	988 \pm 98 (887–1140)	-	1020–1140	1080 \pm 100 (920–1170)		847–1153	
Prerectum length	105	109 \pm 15 (87–130)	132	99.0 \pm 9.0 (84–106)	126 \pm 33 (106–212)	180	116 \pm 9 (106–125)	180	?	162 \pm 32 (133–205)		84–212	
Rectum/cloaca length	19	20.3 \pm 1.1 (19–22)	29	19.4 \pm 1.3 (17–21)	20.0 \pm 0.8 (19–22)	22	19.0 \pm 0.8 (18–20)	22	22	?		17–22	
Tail length	45	42.2 \pm 2.9 (38–47)	49	40.7 \pm 2.5 (37–47)	37.6 \pm 3.0 (31–41)	44	40.0 \pm 1.0 (39–43)	44	42–46	42.1 \pm 2.4 (40–47)		31–47	
Spicules length	-	-	38	-	-	40	-	40	-	-		-	
Ventromedian supplements	-	-	5	-	-	5	-	5	-	-		-	

Fig. 1. *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. A: Female, entire. B: Male, entire. C, D: Anterior region, lateral median view. E: Neck region. F: Pharyngeal enlargement. G: Female, anterior genital branch. H: Female, posterior body region. I: Anterior region, in lateral surface view. J: Pharyngo-intestinal junction. K: Vagina region. L: Male posterior body region. M: Intestine-prerectum junction. N: Oviduct-uterus junction. O: Female, caudal region. P: Male, caudal region. Q: Spicule. Scale bars: A, B = 200 μ m; C, D, I, K, Q = 5 μ m; E = 50 μ m; F, J, M–P = 10 μ m; G, H, L = 20 μ m.

Fig. 2. *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. (LM, general morphology). A, F: Female, entire. G: Male, entire. B–D, I: Anterior region, in lateral median view. E: Neck region. H: Anterior region, in lateral surface view. J, K: Lateral chord, showing gland bodies. L: Female, anterior genital branch. M: Pharyngeal expansion, in submedian view focusing on spiral muscular sheath. N: Oviduct-uterus junction. O: Vagina region. P: Pharyngo-intestinal junction, with detail of ventral gland bodies. Q: Pharyngeal enlargement and DN. Scale bars: A, F, G = 200 μm ; B–D, H, I, O = 5 μm ; E = 50 μm ; J, K, N, P, Q = 10 μm ; L, M = 20 μm .

oviduct and uterus. Uterus a wide tube with visible lumen, 48–72 μm or 1.4–1.8 times the corresponding body width long, lacking any differentiation. Sperm cells not observed in the genital tract. Vagina 17–21 μm long, extending inwards one-third to one-half (35–47%) of body diameter: *pars proximalis* 10.5–12 \times 6–6.5 μm with nearly straight walls surrounded by moderately

developed circular muscles, *pars distalis* 6.5–9 \times 8–10 μm . Vulva a short longitudinal slit, surrounded by a local differentiation of the cuticle. Prerectum 4–9, rectum 0.7–0.8 anal body diameters long.

Male: Apparently very rare, only one specimen examined. Genital system poorly developed and probably non-functional. Nevertheless, sexual accessory

Fig. 3. *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. (LM, posterior body region). A: Female, posterior body region. B, C: Male, posterior body region. D: Male, caudal region and spicule. E–G: Female, caudal region. H: Spicule. Scale bars: A–C, F = 20 μm ; D, E, G = 10 μm ; H = 5 μm .

elements are distinct. In addition to the ad-cloacal pair, there are five spaced ventromedian supplements out the range of spicules, with a large hiatus. Spicule dorylaimid, strongly curved ventrad, comparatively robust, 4.5 times as long as wide, and 1.4 times longer than body diameter at cloacal aperture: head occupying 27% of the total length, with somewhat concave dorsal side and slightly convex ventral side, median piece occupying 35% of the maximum width, dorsal hump not appreciable, posterior tip blunt, curvature 120°. Lateral guiding pieces obscure.

Other populations: In addition to the type one, other populations have been studied for comparative purposes (morphometrics in Table 1). All of them show totally comparable morphology, with no significant difference affecting any qualitative feature. Morphometrically, however, they present appreciable variations in many measurements (lengths of body, neck, tail) and ratios, but always with large overlapping in their respective ranges. Conversely, some key traits as lip region diameter, odontostyle length, position of valves at the anterior pharyngeal region, etc. are very constant, with minimum interpopulation variability. Thus, there is no doubt of their belonging to the same species.

Molecular characterization: After sequencing and

editing, six sequences were obtained for phylogenetic analyses. Three 18S rDNA sequences, 1705 bp in length (PX275707–PX275709), showed 98.77% identity to a sequence (AY552969) assigned to *D. virginianus* Cobb, 1913 (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980), showed 98.06% identity to a sequence (AY911972) assigned to *D. tenuidens* Thorne, 1939, showed 97.95% identity to two sequences (PQ877192, PQ877193) assigned to *C. caramborum* García-Ruiz, Abolafia and Peña-Santiago, 2025, and 97.89% and 97.77% with sequences corresponding to *D. montenegricus* Andrassy, 1959 (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980) and *D. parvulus* Thorne, 1939 (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980), respectively (AY284821, AY911968).

Three 28S rDNA sequences, 761 bp in length (PX275710–PX275712), showed 85.15% identity to two sequences (PQ877192, PQ877193) assigned to *C. caramborum* García-Ruiz, Abolafia and Peña-Santiago, 2025, 79.76% with those of *B. bagongshanensis* Wu, Huang, Xie, Wang and Xu, 2017 (KT258984, KT25985), 78.83% identity to *B. coomansi* Golhasan, Heydari, Miraeiz, Abolafia and Peña-Santiago, 2018 (MF363124) and 77.40% with sequences corresponding to *Belondira* sp. (MG921267, MG921268).

Diagnosis: The new species is distinguished by its 1.57–2.43 mm long body, lip region cap-like and

Fig. 4. *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. (LM, pharyngeal differentiation). A, B: Anterior region of neck, showing the spindle-shaped and valve containing differentiation at the slender portion of pharynx. C, D: Detail of the differentiation. Scale bars: A, B = 10 µm; C, D = 5 µm.

Fig. 5. *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. (Female, SEM). A: Anterior body region, lateral view. B, C, E: Lip region, in face view. D, F, G: Lateral body pores. H, I: Female, caudal region. J: Vulva, ventral view. Scale bars: A–C, E, J = 2 μ m; I, H = 5 μ m; D, G, F = 1 μ m.

offset by marked constriction, cheilostom slightly flask-like and with thick and visibly refractive walls bearing distinct circumoral platelets, odontostyle 9–9.5 mm long or almost equal to lip region width, odontophore linear, relatively short neck ($b = 6.1\text{--}9.7$), anterior pharyngeal region weakly muscular and bearing a spindle-shaped and valve containing differentiation behind the odontophore base, pharyngeal expansion 113–157 mm long or 44–54% of total neck length, longitudinal vulva ($V = 50\text{--}57$), tail conoid to subcylindroid (31–46 mm, $c = 37\text{--}59$, $c' = 1.4\text{--}1.9$ in females), spicules 38–40 mm, and five ventromedian supplements with hiatus.

Separation from its relatives: In its general aspect, the new species resembles several representatives of the subgenus *Dorylaimellus* characterized by displaying comparatively long body (more than 1.00 mm vs very often up to 1.0 mm in the remaining species) and short neck (b -ratio more than 6.0 vs very often up to 5.0). These species are: *D. andrassyi* Heyns, 1963 (= *D. pastura* Yeates, 1979), *D. bambesae* De Coninck, 1962, *D. basiri* Jairajpuri, 1965, *D. imitator* Heyns, 1963, *D. indicus* Siddiqi, 1964b (= *D. curvatus* Jairajpuri, 1964), *D. longus* Bohra and Sultana, 2010, *D. murtazai* Baqri, 1991, *D. parindicus* Ahmad and Naz, 2012, *D. pruni* Husain and Khan, 1967 and *D. shamimi* Ahmad and Naz, 2012. The main morphometrics of these species are compiled in table 2 for comparative purposes.

In having a peculiar stomatal nature (slightly flask-like and thick-walled cheilostom, comparatively robust and somewhat fusiform odontostyle, odontophore lacking any appreciable differentiation) and a spindle-shaped differentiation at the anterior pharyngeal region, *D. (D.) grandis* sp. nov. is especially similar to two out the listed species, namely *D. bambesae* and *D. parindicus*. It can be distinguished from *D. bambesae*, originally found in the former Zaire (De Coninck 1962), in its more slender body ($a = 42\text{--}60$ vs $a = 32\text{--}40$) and less rounded and longer female tail ($c' = 1.4\text{--}1.9$ vs $c' = 1.0\text{--}1.3$). [Unfortunately, the original description of *D. bambesae* is not very detailed for comparative purposes. Andrassy (1965) also recorded this species in Ghana, but there is a doubt about the true identity of this material as the general size is appreciably smaller: body length 1.16–1.35 vs 1.69–1.84 mm long, respectively.] The new species differs from *D. parindicus*, at present an Indian endemism, by its larger general size: body length 1.57–2.43 vs 1.2–1.5 mm, odontostyle 9–9.5 vs 5–6 μm , and odontophore 16–16.5 vs 12 μm . The presence (vs absence) of valves at the spindle-shaped differentiation of the anterior pharyngeal region is other difference between them, but this trait is only appreciable in good specimens and might be overlooked in the two previously known species.

Type locality and habitat: Spain, Almería

province, Calar Alto Mountain, where the new species was collected in soil of a Mediterranean brushwood whose dominant plant species were *Stipa tenacissima* L., *Echinopartum boissieri* (Spach) Rothm., *Thymus vulgaris* L. and *Retama* sp.

Other localities and habitats: The new species is widely distributed in the southern of the Iberian Peninsula, where it has been found in more than twenty localities of the provinces of Almería, Granada, Jaén and Málaga, very often associated with natural habitats (oak forests, pine forests, brushwoods), but also present in olive orchards.

Type material: Female holotype, seven female paratypes and one male paratype deposited at the Nematode Collection of the University of Jaén, Spain. Four female paratypes at the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, CSIF, Madrid, Spain.

Etymology: The specific epithet is the Latin term *grandis* = large, due to the large size of the new species compared with its congeners.

DISCUSSION

The subfamily Dorylaimellinae is a diverse nematode group that, according to Andrassy (2009), included 74 valid species. From a morphological perspective, it displays a remarkable variability mainly affecting the lip region (continuous to distinctly offset and cap-like, with or without perioral disc), cheilostom (with or without circumoral pieces/platelets), female genital system (di-ovarian, mono-pro-ovarian or mono-opistho-ovarian) and female tail (long and filiform to short and rounded, including conical elongated, conical, conoid, subcylindrical and clavate shapes). Thus, it is not surprising that the taxonomy of the group was matter of several revisions and some controversy, with up to 15 genera/subgenera were proposed on the basis of different combinations of key traits and/or putting special emphasis on particular features (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980; Siddiqi 1983; Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1992; Andrassy 2009). The system provided by these generic/subgeneric taxa is very useful for practical purposes as it makes easier the separation and identification of species. Nevertheless, whether or not they represent natural (monophyletic) taxa remains an enigma as no cladistic analysis of the group was ever carried out.

The new species herein described is characterized by a combination of at least three relevant features. First, the stomatal armature, including a slightly flask-like and thick-walled cheilostom, a relatively robust and somewhat fusiform odontostyle, and a rod-like odontophore, which might represent not only an apomorphic but also an autapomorphic condition

Table 2. Morphometrics of a selected group of *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus)* species. (See text for additional information)

Character	n	L	a	b	c	c'	V	Ird	odt	odp	neck	ohc	pre	tail	spic	vs	country	Ref. ^a	
Species																			
<i>andrusnyi</i>	14 ♀♀	0.87–1.50	35–47	5.7–9.0	24–33	2.2 ¹	47–57	9 ¹	7.5 ¹	15 ¹	211 ¹	?	?	55 ¹	–	–	South Africa	1	
	4 ♂♂	1.40–1.60	38–46	6.4–8.4	24–32	?	–	?	?	?	179 ¹	?	?	50 ¹	?	5	–	–	5
	♀	1.05	47	6.7	31	?	50	6–7	6	9	157 ¹	?	?	34 ¹	–	–	–	–	–
	♂	0.89	43	5.5	27	?	–	–	6	9	162 ¹	?	?	33 ¹	20	5	India	2	
175 ♀♀	♀	0.94–2.13	28–62	5.7–12.6	22–45	1.5–2.9	47–60	?	5–9	12–16	?	?	?	36–63	–	–	South Africa	3	
	♂	1.25–1.62	37–62	7.0–11.1	23–40	1.6–2.4	–	?	5–8	12–16	?	?	?	37–58	20–39	4–6	–	–	
as <i>D. pastura</i>	11 ♂♂	1.64	51	9.1	33	2.3	49	9	9	12	180	71	?	50	–	–	Botswana	4	
	3 ♂♂	1.55–1.61	52–60	8.8–9.1	35–40	1.7–1.9	–	9	5–8	11–13	170–190	63–73	136	39–46	37–38	3–5	–	–	
	7 ♀♀	1.0–1.2	44–53	6.7–9.0	26–32	2.2–2.9	50–53	7	4–5	10–12	131–146	32–47	61–71	36–43	–	–	India	5	
	3 ♂♂	1.0, 0.9	47, 47	7.7, 5.5	34, 33	1.7	–	7	4	12	135, 164	42–54	85, 63	31, 27	23, 19	5	–	–	
as <i>D. bambesae</i>	22 ♀♀	1.43–1.70	37–51	7.2–9.0	26–39	1.7–2.4	48–52	?	?	?	199 ¹	?	?	65 ¹	–	–	New Zealand	6	
	3 ♀♀	1.69–1.84	32–40	8.2–9.5	46–53	1.0–1.3	50–55	8	6 ¹	14	193–209 ¹	80 ¹	?	35–40 ¹	–	–	Former Zaire	7	
<i>basiri</i>	2 ♀♀	1.16–1.35	40–49	7.6–8.5	31–42	?	52–53	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	Ghana	8	
	6 ♀♀	1.2–1.5	48–54	6.0–6.5	17–21	5.0 ¹	45–48	6 ¹	5	20	219 ¹	?	?	78 ¹	–	–	India-UP	9	
<i>imitator</i>	6 ♀♀	1.00–1.32	32–44	6.1–7.7	32–40	1.5	48–52	9 ¹	7.5 ¹	12	183 ¹	?	?	33 ¹	–	–	South Africa	1	
	14 ♀♀	1.00–1.44	32–57	6.1–10.1	32–53	1.4–1.9	48–56	?	5–8	11–14	?	?	?	27–32	–	–	South Africa	3	
<i>indicus</i>	6 ♀♀	1.3–1.5	45–56	7.0–8.5	39–46	1.7	51–53	8	5–6	12–13	189 ¹	70–78	?	35 ¹	–	–	India-UP	10	
	34 ♀♀	1.00–1.68	41–53	6.7–9.0	35–48	1.5–2.0	48–55	?	6–7	11–12	?	?	37–66	?	–	–	India	11	
	5 ♀♀	1.48–1.61	46–52	8.2–9.0	45–48	1.5–1.6	50–52	?	7	12–13	?	?	?	?	–	–	India-Sikkim	12	
as <i>D. curvatus</i>	5 ♀♀	1.2–1.4	39–56	7.3–8.0	35–40	1.6 ¹	50–53	?	?	?	178 ¹	?	?	32 ¹	–	–	India-Assam	13	
<i>longus</i>	8 ♀♀	1.41–1.48	54–59	8.0–9.1	37–47	1.6–1.9	49–52	8–9	6–8	11–12	161–175	60–76	35–50	30–40	–	–	India-Rajasthan	14	
	♀	1.5	60	8.5	43	1.8	51	?	6	13	176 ¹	?	?	35	–	–	India-Uttarakhan	15, 16	
<i>murtazai</i>	3 ♀♀	1.25–1.39	36–45	7.6–7.8	17–18	3.1–3.6	46–50	7.5–9.0	7–8	12–13	160–178 ¹	59 ¹	33–40	73–76	–	–	India-Sikkim	12	
<i>parindicus</i>	11 ♀♀	1.2–1.5	38–48	6.3–8.9	35–45	1.3–1.8	47–54	7–8	5–6	12	160–195	60–82	80–120	30–40	–	–	India-Assam	17	
<i>pruni</i>	7 ♀♀	1.4–1.5	50–56	8.0–9.0	40–47	1.8	57–59	?	?	?	175 ¹	55–60	?	35 ¹	–	–	India-UP	18	
<i>shamimi</i>	8 ♀♀	1.1–1.2	34–44	6.1–7.4	19–23	2.6–3.3	47–50	6–8	7–8	10–14	155–185	55–78	65–100	50–60	–	–	India-Mehalaya	17	

Acronyms: Demanian indices (de Man, 1880): a = body length/body diameter, b = body length/pharynx length, c = body length/tail length, c' = tail length/anal body diameter, V = (distance from anterior region to vulva/body length) x100, Ird: Lip region diameter, odt: Odontostyle length, odp: Odontophore length, Neck: Neck length, phe: Pharyngeal expansion length, pre: Prerectum length, tail: Tail length, spic: Spicule length, vs: Ventromedian supplements. ^a References: 1: Heyns (1963), 2: Chaturvedi and Khera (1979), 3: Jordana and Heyns (1984), 4: De Bruin and Heyns (1993), 5: Kumar and Ahmad (2024), 6: Yeates (1979), 7: De Coninck (1962), 8: Andrassy (1965), 9: Jairajpuri (1965), 10: Siddiqi (1964b), 11: Baqri and Jairajpuri (1968), 12: Baqri (1991), 13: Jairajpuri (1964), 14: Bohra and Sultana (2010), 15: Sharma (2014), 16: Sharma (2018), 17: Ahmad and Naz (2012), 18: Husain and Khan (1967). ¹ Calculated from illustrations and/or other morphometrics. ² Including specimens of two or more populations.

Fig. 6. Bayesian inference tree from the newly sequenced *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. based on sequences of the 18S rDNA region. Bayesian posterior probabilities (%) are given for each node. The scale bar shows the number of substitutions per site. Sequences of Belondiridae taxa highlighted in yellow, green and red.

Fig. 7. Bayesian inference tree from the newly sequenced *Dorylaimellus (Dorylaimellus) grandis* sp. nov. based on sequences of the 28S rDNA region. Bayesian posterior probabilities (%) are given for each clade. The scale bar shows the number of substitutions per site. Sequences of Belondiridae taxa highlighted in yellow, green and blue.

compared with its closest relatives, for instance, the representatives of the subgenus *Dorylaimellus* (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1980; Siddiqi 1983). Second, the presence of a spindle-shaped area bearing valves at the anterior pharyngeal region certainly is an apomorphic state, also known to occur in other belondirid genera (Nair and Coomans 1973; Peña-Santiago 2021a; Peña-Santiago and Abolafia 2023), but not in *Dorylaimellus*-like taxa. Third, the relatively short neck (b -ratio exceeding 6.0, often more) should be regarded as a derived condition, also observed in several representatives of the subgenus *Dorylaimellus* (see above) as well as in very few other long-tailed Dorylaimellinae, for instance, *D. filamentosus* Siddiqi, 1983 ($b = 6.9\text{--}10.4$, $c' = 11\text{--}14$) and *D. salvus* Siddiqi, 1968 ($b = 6.5\text{--}8.0$, $c' = 8\text{--}12$). The study of *D. (D.) grandis* sp. nov., instead of shedding some light on the Dorylaimellinae taxonomy, raises new uncertainties about the matter. Thus, present results have revealed that the subgenus *Dorylaimellus* includes a group of species with comparatively large general size combined with relatively short neck, easy to distinguish from its remaining members (see above). Actually, the authors hesitated about the convenience to propose a new generic/subgeneric taxon to accommodate *D. (D.) grandis* sp. nov. and its closest relatives, *D. bambesae* and *D. parindicus*, which also have in common their stomatal structure and the presence of a spindle-shaped (probably valvated) differentiation at the anterior pharyngeal region. Nevertheless, such action was considered to be premature.

Unfortunately, the availability of molecular data for Dorylaimellinae representatives is very limited, truly a serious inconvenience to elucidate their evolutionary relationships. Actually, the results of the analyses of 18S- and 28S-rDNA sequences herein obtained, presented in the trees of figures 6 and 7, respectively, did not reveal totally comparable phylogenies. Thus, in the 18S tree, the new species forms part of a maximally supported clade that includes all members of two belondirid subfamilies, namely Belondirinae Thorne, 1939 and Dorylaimellinae (highlighted in green and yellow, respectively). The topology of this tree contains at least two points of interest. On the one hand, the new species appears as the sister group of the large, maximally supported subclade made up of other representatives of *Dorylaimellus* plus several Belondirinae genera, an indication that Dorylaimellinae might not be a monophyletic taxon. On the other hand, Belondirinae representatives form part of two maximally supported and separated subclades, an argument against the monophyly of this subfamily too. For its part, the 28S shows that Dorylaimellinae and Belondirinae taxa form a clade (highlighted in yellow

and green, respectively) that does not find good support, only 54%. Nevertheless, the sequences of this clade are grouped into two maximally supported subclades, as follows: (((*D. grandis* sp. nov. + *Capitellus*) + *Belondira*)) + *Axonchium*-like genera), with the *Axonchium*-like genera being the sister group of the remaining taxa, evidence in favour of recovering the subfamily Axonchiinae Thorne, 1964, traditionally (Jairajpuri and Ahmad 1992; Andrassy 2009) regarded as identical to Belondirinae.

CONCLUSIONS

The finding and characterization of the new species herein described confirm the existence of an intricate scenario for elucidating both the phylogeny and the taxonomy of Dorylaimellinae in particular, and of Belondiridae in general. On the one hand, the morphological heterogeneity of the group is even more complex than usually assumed as the new taxon displays an interesting and remarkable combination of key morphological features. On the other hand, evolutionary relationships are not well-established as the phylogenies derived from the molecular analyses significantly differ depending on the gene considered.

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Competing interests: M. Garca-Ruiz, A.N. Ruiz-Cuenca, J. Abolafia and R. Pea-Santiago declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of data and materials: Holotype and paratype have been deposited at the Nematode

Collection of the University of Jaén, Spain. The DNA sequence have been deposited in the GenBank database.

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